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Avifaunal Diversity of Urban Green Spaces of National Capital Territory of Delhi, India

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Abstract

The presence of small green spaces in the urban areas in the form of parks and gardens provides shelter to different species of resident and migratory birds. There is a need for long term documentation of avifaunal diversity which exists in such urban natural environment. This study has been conducted in urban parks of Delhi viz, (i) Hudco Park, (ii) Lodhi Garden, (iii) Siri Fort Park, and (iv) Sanjay Lake Park. All four sites are located in the heart of the South and East Delhi. Bird species were recorded using random surveys in the parks, open areas, across the habitations and along the avenue trees during the period 2017-2022. A total of 62 species and sub-species of birds have been recorded from all four sites, belonging to 13 orders, 35 families and 51 genera. Of these, 50 (81%) are residents and 12 (19%) are migrants. The number of sightings for 13 birds was very common, 18 birds were common, 19 birds were occasional and 12 birds were rare.

Keywords: Urban green spaces; Delhi; Avifaunal diversity; Migratory birds; Resident birds

Introduction

Birds are the only feathered creatures in the world, which are known to be the flying gems of sky. Of about 10,000 species of birds reported globally, India has 1263 species, representing 23 orders, 107 families, and 498 genera, which in turn represents the global avian diversity by about 64%, 45% and 21%, respectively (Jayadevan et al., 2016). Country's diverse climatic conditions, from moist tropical to the cold arctic of the Himalayan ranges, the vast hot desert cold grounds in hilly tracts has endowed it with this high range of species. Maximum numbers of species found in India are resident; however, some arrive as migrants especially in the winter months. The presence of small green spaces in the urban areas in the form of parks and gardens provides shelter to different species of resident and migratory birds. Small green spaces consisted of water bodies and healthy vegetation cover, act as a micro-ecosystem. Such spaces not only provide shelter to numerous bird species and other small animals, including mammals, amphibians, reptiles, butterflies, honeybees, insects and micro-fauna but also serve towards the pollination process and filter pollutants from the atmosphere. High bird diversity in urban landscapes has been associated with high densities of trees and the presence of large green spaces connected to each other (Evans et al., 2009; Beninde et al., 2015).

The National Capital Territory of Delhi (28° 39'13.72" N, 77°13'44.29" E) has two main ecological zones, an extension of the Aravalli Hills on the northwest and the Plains on the east. Delhi is a historical city of India with prehistoric urban forests; the holy river Yamuna, which flows across the region, rejuvenates its rich biodiversity. The Delhi Ridge, which forms the tail end of the Aravalli Mountain range, aroused over a billion years ago, is said to be the heart of the country's capital having over 19 million people. The ridge has witnessed countless disturbances due to excessive developmental and anthropogenic activities. Despite this, the ridge has supported a huge number of wild species to nestle and breed expediently. According to the State of Forest Report 2017, the forest cover in Delhi is 192.41 sq. km, which is 12.97% of the state's geographical area (1483 sq. km). The rainfall of Delhi ranges between 400 mm to 600 mm, however, temperature may rise to 40 – 45 °C during the summer months and generally ranges between 4-5°C during the winter months

(Forest Survey of India, 2017). The region is endowed with thousands of green species in urban areas, which hosts a significant number of avifaunal species. One of the important features of the capital includes presence of avenue trees, parks and gardens in almost every part. These small urban parks support a huge variety of flora and fauna and act as a natural habitat for several resident and migratory birds. Interestingly, the birds that are being hosted by these parks play a crucial role in pollination process, which has been a matter of concern for biodiversity experts since the last one decade. An increase of 3.64 sq. km of the green cover has been observed which can be attributed to the plantation activities and conservation initiatives whereas the decrease in forest cover at some places has been reported because of developmental activities (Forest Survey of India, 2017).

More than 400 bird species have been recorded from Delhi and adjacent areas, including resident and migratory species; of these, nearly 30 species were identified as globally threatened (Avibase, 2019). The Yamuna Biodiversity Park, Aravalli Biodiversity Park, Asola Bhatti Wildlife Sanctuary and Okhla Bird Sanctuary are some of the biodiversity rich sites in the National Capital Region. Though the reports of the abundance of bird species in the territory and adjacent areas have been published time to time, reports on avifauna of urban areas are rare. A study carried out on the interlinkages between the bird species and their habitats in meso-ecosystem and micro-ecosystem of a urban area in Delhi indicated that there is an absence of adequate data on avifauna supported by a micro-urban habitat, such as, a residential colony, commercial area, office complex, industrial area, etc. (Turaga, 2015).

Materials and Methods

Study area: This study was conducted in urban parks of Delhi viz, (i) Hudco Park, (ii) Lodhi Garden, (iii) Siri Fort Park, and (iv) Sanjay Lake Park. All four sites are located in the heart of the South and East Delhi. **Hudco Park:** It is located near one of the oldest shopping mall, Ansal Plaza, south Delhi (28°56.2'23.7"N, 77°22.6'24.5"E). The park is spread over an area of 72843.4 sqm, which consists of several small grass mounts. The area has since developed into one of India's largest, logistically most complex, and widely acclaimed, urban projects incorporating many innovative design and management solutions.

Lodhi Garden: It is located between Safdurjung's Tomb and Khan Market in south Delhi on Lodhi Road (28°59.4'49.6"N, 77°22.0'81.7"E). The garden covers an area of about 364217 sqm, endowed with beautiful monuments and tombs. With its undulating walking tracks, fringed with ancient trees and flowering plants, the garden is an amalgamation of a historic past encompassed within today's Delhi. The park serves as a natural heritage site and helps in maintaining the quality of urban environment.

Siri Fort Park: Spread over an area of 161874 sqm (28°55'37.86"N, 77°22'77.50"E), it is located near Siri Fort Sport Complex. Park is maintained by Delhi Development Authority. This is one of the best urban parks, which holds a wide range of diverse flora and fauna. A feel of wilderness can be observed easily while walking across various tracks throughout the park. Some of the large old trees of the park witness our historical forest management and conservation initiatives undertaken in the past. The park also serves as a natural repository of avian fauna in Delhi, wherein a number of birds can be observed year-round. Some of the plant species recorded from these 3 sites (viz. Hudco Park, Lodhi Garden and Siri Fort Park) are *Cassia fistula* (Amaltas), *Ficus religiosa* (Pipal), *Ficus virens* (White Fig), *Bombax ceiba* (Semal), *Bauhinia variegata* (Kachnar), *Callistemon viminalis* (Weeping Bottle-brush), *Polyalthia longifolia* (Ashok), *Pithecellobium dulce* (Jungle Jalebi), *Tabebuia rosea* (Rosy Trumpet Tree), *Alstonia scholaris* (Blackboard tree), *Ficus benghalensis* (Indian Banyan), *Mimusops elengi* (Maulsari), *Morus alba* (Mulberry), *Platyclusus orientalis* (Morpankhi), *Lawsonia inermis* (Hena) and *Roystonea regia* (Royal Palm).

Sanjay Lake Park: It is an artificial lake located in Trilokpuri, Mayur Vihar East Delhi (28°36'52.61"N, 77°18'11.83"E). The site falls under the low-lying area of the old floodplains in East Delhi, which was the receptacle of rainwater drainage. The park was developed by Delhi Development Authority in 1970s, but was opened for locals in the year 1982. The lush green forest of the park serves as a repository of a number of residential birds and the lake in the park attracts a number of migratory birds during the winter. The lake is mainly fed by rainwater and the back flowing water of river Yamuna blesses the lake. However, during adverse weather conditions, the water level of the lake dried also. City forest and residential colonies surrounds the park, and park has been serving as a natural refuge for several avifaunal species. During the last 3-4 years, the Government of Delhi made efforts to restore the pristine ecosystem of the park, by reviving the lake, water augmentation and use of treated water from the sewage treatment plants. Spread over an area of approximately

17 hectares, the park has unique urban floral diversity, which mainly includes *Prosopis juliflora* (Mexican thorn), *Bombax ceiba* (Semal), *Ficus religiosa* (Pipal), *Plumeria rubra* (Plumeria), *Ficus virens* (Pilkhan), *Cassia fistula* (Amaltas), *Derris indica* (Karanj), *Roystonea regia* (Royal Palm) and *Polyalthia longifolia* (Ashok tree).

Fig. 1. Some of the bird's pictures in the study area (A-H) namely: A. White eye, B. Common Hoopoe, C. White-throated Kingfisher, D. Jacobin Cuckoo, E. Black Drongo, F. Dusky Crag Martin, G. White wagtail and H. Brown headed Barbet (Photo credit: Ritesh Joshi)

Bird sampling: Bird species were recorded using random surveys in the parks, open areas, across the habitations and along the avenue trees during the period 2017-2022. All the parks were surveyed randomly year-round from 5.00 AM to 10.00 AM & 5.00 PM to 7.30 PM in summer and from 6.00 AM to 11.00 AM & 4.00 PM to 6.00 PM in winter. About eight to ten days (Saturday and Sunday) have been spent every month in the collection of field data. Birds were not surveyed in extreme weather conditions like during rains, heavy winds, fog. Field binocular (Nikon Action Series, 10×50 CF) and a Canon 200 D SLR Camera was used to observe the birds and to collect photographic evidences. For identification of species, some of the field guides and checklists on birds of Delhi and adjoining areas were considered (Ali, 1941; Ali, 1949; Hutson, 1954; Grimmett et al., 2011; Pande et al., 2012; Birds of Chandigarh, 2018).

Results and Discussion

As per the Avibase, the World Bird Database, more than 400 bird species have been recorded from Delhi, including resident and migratory species; of these, nearly 30 species were identified as globally threatened. In this study, a total of 62 species (Table 1) and sub-species of birds have been recorded from all four sites, belonging to 13 orders, 35 families and 51 genera. Of these, 50 (81%) are residents and 12 (19%) are migrants. The number of sightings for 13 birds was very common, 18 birds were common, 19 birds were occasional and 12 birds were rare. It is interesting to record such a huge number of bird species from small green patches existing across the heart of the city, surrounded by human habitations and motor roads with vehicular traffic.

Maximum sighting occurred were of black kite, rock pigeon, house crow, jungle babbler, purple sunbird, red vented bulbul, common myna and rose-ringed parakeet, followed by rufous treepie, black drongo, oriental magpie robin, red-whiskered bulbul, brahminy starling, Asian pied starling and brown-headed barbet. The population of some birds has exponentially exploded, for example of the blue rock pigeons, which was mainly due to religious and moral feeding. Similarly, the

population of house crows and black kites was recorded increasing mainly because of availability of garbage dumps, convenient breeding sites and ability to acclimatize with any environmental condition. The area is being maintained by the NDMC to keep the area clean; besides, dustbins have also been kept near the footpaths. Local residents have a great affection and care towards these bird species mainly because of its aesthetic value. A number of small pots filled with food and water were found placed by the people at various locations in the area. Some of the bird species can be seen in Figure 1.

Table 1. Checklist of bird species recorded during 2017-2022.

S.No.	Name of the species	Common name	Resident / Migratory
1.	<i>Apus affinis</i>	Little Swift	Resident
2.	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	Indian Grey Hornbill	Resident
3.	<i>Upupa epops</i>	Common Hoopoe	Resident
4.	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	Red-wattled Lapwing	Resident
5.	<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock Pigeon	Resident
6.	<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	Laughing Dove	Resident
7.	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Eurasian Collared Dove	Resident
8.	<i>Treron phoenicoptera</i>	Yellow-footed Green Pigeon	Resident
9.	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	White-throated Kingfisher	Resident
10.	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	Indian Roller	Resident
11.	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Little Green Bee-eater	Summer Migrant
12.	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	Blue tailed bee-eater	Migrant
13.	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Greater Coucal	Resident
14.	<i>Clamator Jacobinus</i>	Jacobin-cuckoo	Migrant
15.	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>	Asian Koel	Summer Migrant
16.	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	Indian Peafowl	Resident
17.	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	Common Tailor Bird	Resident
18.	<i>Prinia inornata</i>	Plain prinia	Resident
19.	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	Ashy Prinia	Resident
20.	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	House Crow	Resident
21.	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	Large-billed Crow	Resident
22.	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	Rufous Treepie	Resident
23.	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	Black Drongo	Resident
24.	<i>Euodice malabarica</i>	Indian Silverbill	Resident
25.	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	Wire-tailed Swallow	Resident
26.	<i>Ptyonoprogne concolor</i>	Dusky Crag Martin	Resident
27.	<i>Lanius schach</i>	Long-tailed Shrike	Resident
28.	<i>Argya malcolmi</i>	Large Grey Babbler	Resident
29.	<i>Turdoides striata</i>	Jungle Babbler	Resident
30.	<i>Terpsiphone paradisi</i>	Indian Paradise-flycatcher	Summer Migrant
31.	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	White wagtail	Migrant
32.	<i>Oenanthe fusca</i>	Brown Rock-chat	Resident
33.	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	Oriental Magpie-robin	Resident
34.	<i>Saxicoloides fulicatus</i>	Indian Robin	Resident
35.	<i>Cyanecula svecica</i>	Bluethroat	Migrant
36.	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	Pied Bushchat	Resident
37.	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	Purple Sunbird	Resident
38.	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House Sparrow	Resident
39.	<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	Common Chiffchaff	Winter/Passage Migrant
40.	<i>Phylloscopus humei</i>	Hume's leaf warbler	Winter Migrant
41.	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	Baya weaver	Resident
42.	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	Red-vented Bulbul	Resident
43.	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	Red-Whiskered Bulbul	Resident
44.	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Common Myna	Resident
45.	<i>Pastor roseus</i>	Rosy Starling	Passage Migrant
46.	<i>Sturnia pagodarum</i>	Brahminy Starling	Resident
47.	<i>Gracupica contra</i>	Asian Pied Starling	Resident
48.	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	Lesser White-throat	Winter Migrant
49.	<i>Zosterops palpebrosus</i>	Oriental White-eye	Resident
50.	<i>Psilopogon haemacephalus</i>	Coppersmith barbet	Resident
51.	<i>Psilopogon zeylanicus</i>	Brown-headed Barbet	Resident
52.	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	Black-rumped flameback	Resident
53.	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	Plum-headed Parakeet	Resident

54.	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Rose-ringed Parakeet	Resident
55.	<i>Psittacula eupatria</i>	Alexandrine Parakeet	Resident
56.	<i>Athene brama</i>	Spotted Owlet	Resident
57.	<i>Otus bakkamoena</i>	Indian Scops-owl	Migrant
58.	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Black Kite	Resident
59.	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	Shikra	Resident
60.	<i>Neophron percnopterus</i>	Egyptian Vulture	Resident
61.	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle Egret	Resident
62.	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	Red-naped Ibis	Resident

Conclusion

Urban green spaces are important areas, which support the bird's diversity in cities. However, we have a limited understanding of their functioning and ecosystem services they provide in managing biodiversity at local and landscape level. Urban green spaces are also useful in mitigating the negative consequences of air pollution. Today, when the population in the cities is increasing rapidly, landscape-level urban planning is important to manage and protect biodiversity in metropolitan cities. Urban green spaces provide important recreational, social and psychological benefits to stressed city residents. NCT of Delhi is blessed with urban parks having indigenous floral and faunal species. Environs of the historical monuments, flood plains of river Yamuna and presence of Delhi ridge also facilitate in enriching the diverseness of the area. It has been reported that some of the factors responsible for the decline in the number of bird species in urban areas are reduction in native vegetation, unplanned urban expansion, climate change and contamination of air. The city birds are also impacted by the garbage and plastic waste, deposited near the open areas. The survival of house sparrow, which is completely associated with human beings, is on the decline in many parts of the country, mainly due to modern architecture, which normally doesn't have open spaces. Plantation of some fruit-bearing species would be helpful in attracting various residential and migratory birds to stay in the city parks. This would not only restore the urban ecosystem but also serve in increasing pollination through management and conservation of pollinators and in maintaining the air quality. Some small water pools could be constructed, to attract the birds, especially during the summer. More or less, long-term conservation programmes must be adopted in order to manage and protect the natural ecosystems and bird diversity present in the NCT of Delhi and the entire NCR.

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Author Contributions

RJ and KP conceived the concept, surveyed, analyzed the data, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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